

USING MATRIX MODELS FOR DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ECOLOGY IN THE DESIGNED ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE STATISTICAL SYSTEM

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The integration of various spheres is a feature of modern economic development, these include economic theory, mathematics, and programming.

In practical processes, research work of statistical systems, as well as in many other systems, solving various problems with the help of artificial intelligence means using new technologies. Project developments provide an opportunity for the development of these areas, the efficiency of the functioning of the entire sphere of the economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

This paper presents a model, the implementation of which with the help of the designed artificial intelligence, reflects the importance and further development of this direction. The model reflects matrix modeling. A conditional example is considered.

The relevance of the issues of research into the digital economy can be represented by the words in the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis, held on January 24, 2020, that “accelerated transition to the digital economy will become our priority task for the next five years.

...in order to consistently continue and bring to a new modern level the work we have begun to develop the sphere of science and education, educate our youth as individuals with deep knowledge, high culture and spirituality, and form a competitive economy, I propose declaring 2020 in our country the Year of Development of Science, Education and the Digital Economy.” [1].

The digital economy is a system of implementing economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital technologies. Sometimes it is also expressed in terms such as the Internet economy, new economy or web economy.

In 1995, American programmer Nicholas Negroponte introduced the term "digital economy" into practice. Now politicians, economists, journalists, entrepreneurs from all over the world - almost everyone - are engaged in this activity.

The digital economy is not another economy that needs to be created from scratch. This means that by creating new technologies, platforms and business models and implementing them into everyday life, we are transferring the existing economy to a new system [2].

Digitalization of economic processes is becoming a complex trend, covering not only the immediate information and communication network, but also all areas of the country's economic activity.

The digital economy revolution is being felt strongly in online commerce, digital agriculture, smart grids, driverless vehicles and personalized healthcare.

The digital economy, or, in other words, the web economy, is a system of economic, social and cultural relations organized using modern digital technologies.

The digital economy is becoming an everyday reality in modern society, and its use increases the efficiency of all industries.

The possibilities of using modern computer technologies are increasing both qualitatively and quantitatively – almost all operations can be performed via a computer: paying money, ordering a ticket, searching for necessary information, etc.

In the era of digital economy, information plays a vital role, it becomes the main intangible asset of great value.

At the present stage, the main trend in the development of information is the improvement of computer technologies together with achievements in the field of artificial intelligence and communications, that is, information is becoming one of the main social values of society in the world.

Information technologies have become an important component of the process of using information resources by society; they have gone through several stages of evolution, and their exchange is based primarily on the emergence of more modern technological means of searching and processing information.

Information systems play a key role in the digital economy. For a telecom operator, such systems are primarily operational support systems and business support systems. Since they represent a category of support for internal business process applications, their change is a response to changes in business processes.

Of course, there is the question of attracting specialists to the digital sector. For example, in the field of digital economy, should we count engineers and economists who design buildings for YandexTaxi drivers or communications equipment? However, in reality, this does not matter much. What is more interesting is not the absolute size of the indicator, but its dynamics in a coordinate system that does not change from year to year. This approach has many strengths, including:

- the indicator should be measured both in the share of the working population and in absolute money;
- originating from the system of macroeconomic indicators, it should reflect precisely the "digital" and precisely the "economy";
- associated with the dynamics of demand for both digital technologies and personnel;
- along with its brevity and conciseness, it fundamentally changes the views on what and where needs to be developed to increase the value of the indicator from year to year.

The rapid growth of computer technologies in various spheres of human activity, on the one hand, has made it possible to ensure high achievements in these areas, and on the other hand, has become a source of unpredictable and harmful consequences for human society.

Society has its positive and negative sides in different periods of development. According to various aspects of public information, the World Bank in its review "Digital Dividends" for 2016 includes the following positive aspects of the development of the digital economy:

- increasing labor productivity;
- increasing the competitiveness of companies;
- reducing production costs;
- creating new jobs;
- eliminating poverty and social inequality.

These are just a few examples of how the digital economy is positively impacting our lives by providing many opportunities to the average user and thereby expanding market opportunities.

However, along with numerous benefits, digital transformation is not without certain risks:

- risk of cyber threats;
- use information about people to control their behavior;
- increase in unemployment, disappearance of some professions;
- failure in digital education and, as a result, failure in welfare, etc.

The vital interests of entities (state, legal and natural persons) participating in automated communication processes, as a rule, consist in the fact that information concerning their economic, political and other aspects of their activities, confidential commercial information and personal data are open and protected from unauthorized access, illegal use must be protected.

In this model, we also included a row and column called ecology.

Taking into account the ecology in each industry, as well as environmental indicators such as quality for life, land, water, clean air allows for a more qualitative consideration of the rational functioning of each subsystem and the entire system as a whole.

Improving the environment through industries - direct connection and feedback - the impact of the environment on each industry is an innovative process that, with the help of the digital economy indicated in the previous row and column, as well as with the entire artificial intelligence system, can solve many issues and transform, transform towards greater positive changes in the entire society as a whole.

Of the many existing models, in this case, we will consider the inter-industry balance of production and distribution of products - a tool for analyzing and planning the structure of social production, taking into account the complex interrelations of industries in the production sphere.

From the first literary sources of the 60s of the last century, the familiar materials show that the inter-industry balance characterizes the process of formation and use of the total social product in a detailed industry context. By detailing the general proportions of the national economy, reflected by the most important component of the balance of the entire economy - the balance of the social product, the inter-sectoral balance at the same time synthesizes into a single system the private material balances that characterize the sources of resource formation and the use of individual types of products in the national economy.

The mathematical model of inter-industry balance was developed by V. Leontiev (later a professor at Harvard University, USA). The inter-industry balance scheme is a synthesis of two tables, one of which characterizes the detailed structure of production costs for individual types of products, and the other - the structure of distribution of products in the national economy.

The inter-industry balance in physical terms consists of two sections. The first section reflects the sources of formation of production resources. The second section characterizes the directions of use of production resources for current production consumption (in the context of the same types of products for which the formation of resources is taken into account in the balance, which ensures the chessboard construction of this section of the balance) and for final consumption [3].

In this study, we decided to consider the digital economy and ecology in the inter-industry balance system, to determine what part of each industry is the digital economy and ecology. As data from developed countries show, the influence of the digital economy on all other industries increases over time. Ultimately, this significantly affects the overall GDP. The mutual influence of ecology and the entire system as a whole will also increase.

Including ecology in the balance also leads to the collection, processing, and analysis of statistical data in this area. In the artificial intelligence system, this is not only possible, but opens up great opportunities for the transformation and restoration of the ecology of small and large territories.

Such opportunities are provided to us by the developed system of artificial intelligence and quantum technology, which can be discussed in subsequent articles.

Let us consider the model of inter-industry balance of production and distribution of products, where the digital economy is presented as one of the branches of material production and the new sphere - ecology follows it (Fig. 1)

Consuming industries Producing industries	1	2	3	4	5	Final products	Gross output
	1. Industry	2. Agriculture	3. Other branches of material production	4. Digital economy	5. Ecology		
1 Industry	X ₁₁	X ₁₂	X ₁₃	X ₁₄	X ₁₅	Y ₁	X ₁
2. Agriculture	X ₂₁	X ₂₂	X ₂₃	X ₂₄	X ₂₅	Y ₂	X ₂
3. Other branches of material production	X ₃₁	X ₃₂	X ₃₃	X ₃₄	X ₃₅	Y ₃	X ₃
4. Digital economy	X ₄₁	X ₄₂	X ₄₃	X ₄₄	X ₄₅	Y ₄	X ₄
5. Ecology	X ₅₁	X ₅₂	X ₅₃	X ₅₄	X ₅₅	Y ₅	X ₅
Clean production	Y ₁	Y ₂	Y ₃	Y ₄	Y ₅	-	-
Gross output	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	-	

It should be noted here that this model is a statistical model.

It is developed for a specific period.

Let's consider the model using a specific example:

Consuming	1	2	3	4	5	Final	Gross
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industries	1. Industry	2. Agriculture	3. Other branches of material production	4. Digital economy	5. Ecology	products	output
Producing industries							
1 Industry	30.6	10.3	5.3	12	3	68	114.2
2. Agriculture	15.3	4.9	0.8	8	3	28	49.0
3. Other branches of material production	10.2	2.1	2.1	4	3	16	30.4
4. Digital economy	12	8	4	24	1	-	-
5. Ecology	3	3	3	1	10	-	-
Clean production	58.1	31.7	22.4	-	-	-	-
Gross output	114.2	49.0	30.4	24	10	Валовая продукция: 169.6 +24+10=203.6	

In this table, we have presented and highlighted the digital economy and ecology in order to clearly see these areas, their state for a particular period, observe changes and, accordingly, obtain more detailed information on gross output both by industry and the indicator as a whole.

Companies that lead the digital revolution not only reap significant benefits, but also take on significant risks. One of the most pressing issues today is ensuring the information security of various government agencies and commercial organizations, and personal data. Recently, more and more large volumes of information, including information important to individuals, organizations or countries, are stored, processed and transmitted using automated systems. An information processing system is a set of hardware and software, as well as human actions and information processing methods necessary to perform automated information processing.

Fifteen years ago, when the information economy was in its infancy, according to research by information security specialists, by this time there had been significant changes in the understanding of data protection.

When talking about the economic feasibility of information security measures, many people first of all think about protection from viruses and hackers, however, according to reports from leading organizations, the greatest damage over the last decade has been caused by insiders (company employees).

Thus, according to these studies, the damage caused by careless and illegal actions of employees is several times greater than the damage caused by viruses and hacker attacks, as well as the introduction of malicious programs directly to obtain information. This happened in 2007, when the number of incidents caused by internal and external offenders was comparable.

Ensuring strict information security requirements requires appropriate measures at all stages of the information technology life cycle. The development of these measures will be carried out after the risk analysis and response selection have been completed. Periodic verification of compliance with the security policy of the current regime, certification of compliance of the information system (technology) with the requirements of the specified security standard are mandatory components of these plans. All of the above is risk management.

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Thus, in the inter-industry balance, the presentation of the digital economy and ecology allows not only economists and management personnel to make appropriate analyses and conclusions, but also all specialists in these areas to more fully use the presented information in a shorter time frame, corresponding to real indicators. The indicators are presented in detail by industry, as well as as a general indicator, which became possible with the emergence of such concepts as “Big Data”, blockchain, cloud spaces in the virtual world, etc. Such measurements in the economy make it possible to constantly improve its quality. This applies to such unforeseen situations as a pandemic, changes in the environment, changes in the structure of industries due to the emergence of new technologies, etc.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАННАЯ ЛИТЕРАТУРА

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